

Use of Assistive Technologies in Rehabilitation

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Abstract - This paper presents an integrative review on the use of assistive technologies in rehabilitation processes, highlighting their classifications, therapeutic applications, and future perspectives. Technologies were organized by complexity with emphasis on tools such as orthoses, powered wheelchairs, robotic exoskeletons, brain-computer interfaces, and virtual reality systems. The analysis showed that these tools promote significant gains in motor, cognitive, and communicative rehabilitation, contributing to greater autonomy and quality of life. Recent studies reinforce the importance of device personalization and integration with evidence-based clinical practices. The article also discusses ethical, economic, and social challenges related to access and sustainability of these technologies, proposing the need for inclusive public policies and a collective commitment to equity. It concludes that assistive technologies are essential not only for functional performance, but also for promoting the dignity and social inclusion of people with disabilities.

Keywords: assistive technologies, rehabilitation, inclusion, neurorehabilitation, autonomy.

I- INTRODUCTION

Assistive technology (AT) encompasses an interdisciplinary field consisting of resources and services specifically designed to promote functionality, autonomy, and inclusion for people with disabilities. According to Bersch and Tonolli [1], resources refer to any item, equipment, product, or system mass - produced or custom-made - designed to expand, maintain, or improve an individual's functional capabilities. Services involve technical or professional support that enables the selection, acquisition, and appropriate use of these resources.

The Technical Assistance Committee of the National Coordination for the Integration of Persons with Disabilities [2] reinforces this perspective by defining AT as a set of practices, methodologies, strategies, and devices, covering people with disabilities, reduced mobility, or the elderly, with the goal of promoting their social participation and functional independence. Brazilian legislation also recognizes the importance of AT, particularly through the Brazilian Inclusion Law (Law No. 13.146/2015), which guarantees access to products, services, and public policies that promote mobility and quality of life. Complementary regulations, such as Decree No. 5.296/2004, reinforce the need for

integrated and ongoing actions to provide and monitor these technologies. In the context of the categorization of resources, a notable proposal is structured based on the guidelines of the Americans with Disabilities Act – ADA (1994), adapted by Tonolli and Bersch, which aims to functionally organize the devices and guide their clinical prescription, research, and development. This classification differentiates assistive technology (AT) resources from strictly medical or hospital technologies, including devices traditionally overlooked, such as aids for daily living, whose application is central to promoting autonomy [3]. Among the main categories of AT resources are:

- Aids for daily living: utensils that facilitate tasks such as eating, personal hygiene, and dressing, including adapted cutlery and grab bars;
- Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC): symbolic boards, speech-generating devices, specialized software, and eye-tracking systems;
- Computer accessibility: expanded keyboards, alternative mice, screen readers, and voice recognition software;
- Environmental control systems: devices that allow remote control of home appliances and residential equipment;
- Accessible architectural designs: physical adaptations in buildings such as ramps, elevators, and accessible restrooms;
- Orthoses and prostheses: orthopedic or cognitive devices intended to replace or functionally supplement body parts;
- Postural alignment aids: anatomical cushions, backrests, and body positioners that promote alignment and comfort;
- Mobility aids: manual or motorized wheelchairs, walkers, and scooters;
- Technologies for people with visual impairments: magnifiers, screen enlargers, OCR readers, and braille materials;
- Vehicle adaptations: hand controls, lifting platforms, and adapted vehicles for transportation or independent driving;

- Technologies for people with hearing impairments: hearing aids, visual alert systems, and TTY devices.

The systematization of these resources is essential to support clinical decisions, guide public policies, and foster technological development, acting as a tool to promote accessibility in different contexts.

From the perspective of contemporary rehabilitation, the integration of assistive technologies into therapeutic processes not only compensates for functional limitations but also enhances residual capabilities, promoting neuroplasticity and functional reorganization [4]. Evidence shows that the systematic use of assistive technology (AT) leads to significant improvements in users' motor, cognitive, and communicative functionality [5].

The current paradigm of evidence-based rehabilitation advocates for the use of technologies that are effective, culturally appropriate, and economically viable [6]. In this context, AT emerges as an essential tool for person-centered interventions, aligned with the principles of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health – CIF [7].

The growing diversity of technological resources and the expanding scientific evidence regarding their effectiveness underscore the importance of integrative reviews to consolidate accumulated knowledge. Recent studies indicate significant advances in the use of AT in various contexts, such as mobility, brain-computer interfaces, mobile applications, and virtual reality [8].

However, the interdisciplinary fragmentation of knowledge and the methodological heterogeneity of studies hinder a comprehensive and integrated understanding of the field. Added to this is the rapid pace of technological innovation, which demands constant and systematic updates to the scientific literature [9].

II- METHODOLOGY

This is an integrative literature review, conducted according to systematized methodological steps: formulation of the guiding question, selection of descriptors and Boolean operators, establishment of inclusion and exclusion criteria, extraction of relevant data, critical evaluation of studies, interpretation of results, and synthesis of findings. The integrative review was chosen because it allows the inclusion of studies with different methodological designs, providing a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation [10].

The literature search was carried out using recognized electronic databases: PubMed (U.S. National Library of Medicine), Taylor & Francis, and Elicit, covering the

period from 2006 to 2024. The following descriptors in English were used: “Assistive Technologies,” “Rehabilitation,” and “Disability and Assistive Technology,” combined using the Boolean operators AND and OR, according to structured search criteria.

Publications from 2006 to 2024 were included, in Portuguese, English, and Spanish, that addressed the use of assistive technologies applied to rehabilitation, with emphasis on the fields of medicine, physical therapy, and occupational therapy. As exclusion criteria, articles with restricted access, studies and applications aimed at non-health-related areas (such as security and entertainment), as well as documents not published in recognized scientific media, were disregarded.

III- DEVELOPEMENT

A. Classification and Types of Assistive Technologies in Rehabilitation

Assistive technologies applied to rehabilitation can be classified based on criteria such as technological complexity level, therapeutic purpose, and area of application. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO 9999) proposes a systematic classification that organizes assistive products into functional categories, aiming to facilitate their identification and use in different rehabilitation contexts [11].

Low-complexity technologies are characterized by simple operation, low cost, and accessible maintenance. This group includes conventional orthoses and prostheses, basic environmental adaptations, and everyday mobility aids. Despite being technically simple, these technologies show high acceptance rates among users and have a direct impact on autonomy and functionality in daily living activities [12] and [13].

Medium-complexity technologies require personalized configuration or specific training for effective use. This category includes motorized wheelchairs, computerized alternative communication systems, and functional electrical stimulation devices. Literature indicates that when integrated into structured rehabilitation programs, these technologies provide significant functional gains, contributing to increased social participation and improved quality of life for users [14].

High-complexity technologies represent the state of the art in assistive rehabilitation. These devices integrate fields such as biomedical engineering, neuroscience, data science, and artificial intelligence, resulting in highly specialized solutions like robotic exoskeletons, brain-computer interfaces (BCIs), therapeutic virtual reality systems with haptic feedback, and next-generation myoelectric prostheses capable of interpreting muscle signals with high precision. Such technologies have demonstrated significant effectiveness in restoring gait,

coordination, and motor control in individuals with neurological injuries, including stroke survivors, amputees, and individuals with spinal cord injuries [15].

BCIs have emerged as promising rehabilitation tools for people with tetraplegia, allowing neural signals to be converted into digital commands, thereby restoring communication and motor control [16]. Exoskeletons, in turn, not only enable assisted mobility but have also been associated with inducing brain plasticity and increasing cognitive engagement during therapy sessions [17].

However, the large-scale implementation of these technologies still faces significant barriers, such as high costs, need for specialized infrastructure, operational complexity, and the requirement for highly trained clinical teams. Other challenges include device personalization, adaptation to individual needs, and user acceptance—critical issues that remain obstacles to progress in the field [18].

Therefore, it is essential that public health and technological innovation policies incorporate strategies for continuous evaluation of these solutions, focusing not only on clinical effectiveness but also on economic feasibility, long-term sustainability, and equitable access—especially in public health systems.

B. Evidence of Effectiveness

Assistive technologies have been successfully applied in various rehabilitation contexts, demonstrating significant benefits in functional recovery, promotion of autonomy, and improved quality of life. Among the main application domains are motor rehabilitation, cognitive rehabilitation, and augmentative and alternative communication (AAC).

In motor rehabilitation, technological resources have been integrated into conventional therapeutic programs with consistent results. Robotic gait systems such as Lokomat and Gait Trainer stand out for their effectiveness in restoring locomotor function in patients with spinal cord injury or stroke, promoting gains in mobility and independence [19]. Evidence from randomized clinical trials indicates that combining traditional physiotherapy with robot-assisted therapy results in significant improvements in gait speed, postural balance, and overall functional performance [20]. In parallel, the use of virtual reality has emerged as an effective complementary tool, enabling immersive motor training environments with real-time feedback, increasing user motivation and allowing for precise measurement of therapeutic progress [21].

In the field of cognitive rehabilitation, assistive technologies include cognitive stimulation applications, interactive software, and memory compensation devices. Computer-based interventions have shown potential in improving executive functions, sustained attention, and working memory, particularly in patients with traumatic brain injury or neurodegenerative diseases such as dementia [22]. Devices such as personal digital assistants,

reminder apps, and electronic calendars—when adapted to users' specific needs—have significantly contributed to maintaining functional independence and improving quality of life [23]. The personalization of cognitive tools, considering the user's profile and daily routine, is considered one of the main determinants of therapeutic success.

Finally, Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) systems, especially those based on digital technologies, have radically transformed the communicative capacity of people with severe speech limitations. Tools such as tablets with specialized software, speech synthesis devices, and eye-tracking interfaces have expanded possibilities for expression and social interaction [24]. Studies indicate that continuous use of AAC technologies not only improves functional communication but also fosters the development of language skills and strengthens social and educational inclusion [25].

C. Challenges, Limitations, and Trends

Despite significant advances, assistive technologies still face important technical challenges. The durability of electronic components under intensive use, the need for specialized maintenance, and technological obsolescence represent significant practical limitations [26]. Additionally, issues of interoperability between different systems and the lack of standardization hinder the effective integration of multiple technologies.

The high acquisition and maintenance costs of advanced assistive technologies constitute a substantial barrier to their widespread implementation in rehabilitation services, especially within public health systems. Cost-effectiveness studies show that although many technologies offer clear therapeutic benefits, high initial investments can limit their adoption, particularly in developing countries [27].

The literature shows that psychosocial factors significantly influence the acceptance and continued use of assistive technologies. Aspects such as self-esteem, perceived stigma, ease of use, and personal relevance emerge as critical determinants of therapeutic success [28]. The need for proper training for both users and professionals constitutes another important challenge.

The integration of artificial intelligence algorithms into assistive technologies represents another important frontier in rehabilitation. Adaptive systems capable of automatically personalizing training parameters according to user progress show potential to optimize therapeutic outcomes [29].

Augmented and mixed reality technologies are emerging as innovative tools for rehabilitation, providing immersive and interactive therapeutic environments. Applications include gait training with enhanced visual feedback, cognitive rehabilitation in contextualized virtual environments, and occupational therapy assisted by mixed reality [30].

IV- SYNTHESIS and DISCUSSION

The integrative analysis of the reviewed studies reveals a complex and evolving landscape of assistive technologies (AT) in rehabilitation. The findings converge on the recognition that ATs are not merely compensatory tools but constitute fundamental elements for optimizing neuroplastic processes and maximizing the potential for functional recovery [31].

Scientific evidence consistently demonstrates that the effectiveness of assistive technologies is intrinsically linked to their systemic integration into rehabilitation programs, transcending the isolated application of devices. This systemic integration involves not only the appropriate selection of technology but also its adaptation to the individual characteristics of the user, proper professional training, and consideration of the sociocultural implementation context [32].

The data analyzed show that technologies of varying complexity can produce significant therapeutic benefits when appropriately prescribed and implemented. Paradoxically, low-complexity technologies often exhibit higher adherence rates than high-complexity ones, suggesting that technological sophistication does not guarantee therapeutic success [33].

A. Mediating Factors of Success

The synthesis of evidence identifies three critical mediating factors for the success of interventions with assistive technologies: personalization, training, and continuous support. Personalization emerges as a fundamental element, going beyond mere physical adaptation of devices to include alignment with users' preferences, goals, and life context [34].

Adequate training, for both users and professionals, is another key determinant. Studies show that structured and progressive training programs lead to better functional outcomes and greater user satisfaction. However, the analysis reveals a significant gap in the standardization of training protocols, with considerable variability in the approaches used [35].

The findings of this review have direct implications for clinical rehabilitation practice. Evidence supports the adoption of a systematic approach to the selection and implementation of assistive technologies, based on a comprehensive assessment of functional needs, personal preferences, and the user's environmental context [36].

The need to develop specific competencies in assistive technologies among rehabilitation professionals emerges as a priority. This includes not only technical knowledge about devices but also skills in assessment, prescription, training, and longitudinal follow-up [37].

The analysis of economic barriers highlights the need for public policies that ensure equitable access to assistive technologies. The findings suggest that investments in medium-complexity technologies may offer a better cost-benefit ratio, considering both therapeutic effectiveness and economic sustainability [38].

Evidence highlights the importance of policies that encourage the research and development of culturally appropriate and economically accessible technologies, especially for developing countries. This includes promoting local innovation and adapting existing technologies to regional realities [39].

The analysis reveals significant methodological limitations in the current literature, including heterogeneity in participant selection criteria, variability in outcome measures, and insufficient long-term follow-up. Robust longitudinal studies are needed to understand the sustained effects of assistive technologies and to identify predictive factors of therapeutic success [40].

The lack of cost-effectiveness studies is another important gap, limiting the ability to make evidence-based decisions regarding health resource allocation. Economic research is essential to support public policies and clinical decisions [41].

The review identified limited representation of various populations in the analyzed studies, including children, older adults, and people with multiple disabilities. This gap limits the generalizability of findings and highlights the need for targeted research for these vulnerable populations [42].

Additionally, there is a scarcity of studies conducted in developing countries, which restricts understanding of the applicability of assistive technologies across different socioeconomic and cultural contexts [43].

V- CONCLUSIONS

This integrative review demonstrates that assistive technologies are effective and essential tools for contemporary rehabilitation, providing measurable benefits across various functional domains. Scientific evidence consistently supports their clinical application, although it also reveals the need for systematic and personalized approaches to maximize therapeutic benefits.

The analysis shows that the success of assistive technologies goes beyond their technical features and is determined by the quality of the initial assessment, alignment with individual needs, proper training, and ongoing support. This understanding redefines the role of rehabilitation professionals, who must act not only as prescribers of devices but also as facilitators in the complex process of technological integration.

The current landscape of assistive technologies in rehabilitation is characterized by the convergence of technological innovation and scientific foundation, resulting in increasingly sophisticated and effective solutions. However, challenges remain, particularly

regarding equitable access, economic sustainability, and the cultural appropriateness of available technologies.

Based on the evidence analyzed, the following recommendations are proposed: training Programs: development of structured professional training programs in assistive technologies, including technical competencies, evaluation skills, and continuous support mechanisms, to ensure dynamic adjustments to both tools and prescriptions.

A. Directions for Future Research

The gaps identified in this review suggest several research directions:

- **Cost-Effectiveness Research:** Conduct comprehensive economic studies to support decisions on resource allocation and the development of evidence-based public policies.
- **Emerging Technologies:** Systematic investigation of emerging technologies, including artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and the Internet of Things, with a focus on their clinical applicability and therapeutic efficacy.
- **Cultural Contexts:** Develop research focused on the cultural appropriateness of assistive technologies and strategies for their adaptation to different socioeconomic realities.

B. Future Perspectives

The future of assistive technologies in rehabilitation lies in the greater integration of technological innovation, therapeutic personalization, and accessibility. Current trends point toward the use of intelligent and adaptive systems that adjust to user needs through the combination of robotics, artificial intelligence, wearable sensors, and virtual reality.

However, to make these innovations broadly accessible, investment is needed in research, professional training, and inclusive public policies. Sustainability and equity remain central challenges, requiring viable and culturally appropriate technological solutions.

More than therapeutic tools, assistive technologies must be understood as instruments for promoting dignity, autonomy, and social inclusion, reaffirming their ethical and strategic role in building a more just society.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex, PPGEUTFPR Curitiba.

CONFLICT of INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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